

SPACETIME–BENDING TRANSFORMATIONS IN AEROACOUSTICS

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The paper deals with the spacetime reinterpretation of the phenomenon of aeroacoustic convection within the framework of the Lorentzian differential geometry. Specifically, the effect of the background aerodynamic velocity field on the propagation of the acoustic disturbances is revisited in terms of spacetime curvature. The analysis explores the local properties of the curved aeroacoustic spacetime to correlate the background aerodynamics with the local value of the Riemann's scalar, and the latter with the convective effect. The metric associated to the aeroacoustic spacetime is compared with that induced by the inverse Taylor transformation, which is based on the $O(M)$ approximation of the convective wave equation. Although limited by the low-speed assumption, the inverse Taylor transformation bends the Minkowskian (i.e., flat) acoustic spacetime taking into account the spatial variation of the background velocity potential. Numerical simulations are conducted to verify and visualise the spacetime properties.

Keywords: acoustic spacetime, Lorentzian geometry, aeroacoustics, Lorentz transformation, Taylor transformation

1. Introduction

The spacetime re-interpretation of the equation governing the propagation of an acoustic perturbation within a moving medium is of high relevance in many modern applications of engineering interest. This is mainly a consequence of the fact that the convective effects, which basically mix space and time derivatives, do not disrupt the formal invariance of the governing equations under the action of Lorentzian transformations, thus making possible the extension to aeroacoustic problems of all the methodologies developed for the manipulation of wave propagation phenomena in media at rest (see, e.g., [4] [1][2] [5] [6] [3] [7]). This research field is of particular interest for the development of acoustic metamaterials operating in a flow, targeted at the design and manufacturing of highly innovative devices for the mitigation of the noise impact of high speed transportation means (aircraft, high-speed trains, automotive...). One of the approaches developed by the author and his collaborators within the framework of the H2020 project AERIALIST (AdvancEd acRaft-noIse-AILeviation devIceS using meTamaterials) makes use of the inverse Taylor's transformation to correct an existing metamaterial design and make it fully functional also in presence of flow (Iemma and Palma [7]). This transformation was introduced by Taylor [10] for the convective correction of aeroacoustic wind-tunnel tests by recasting the $\mathcal{O}(M_\infty)$ approximation of the linearised convective wave equation for the velocity potential in the form of static wave equation. Aim of the present work is to analyse the spacetime structure of the convective equation obtained by

applying the inverse Taylor transform to the static D'Alembertian and compare it to the structure of the full form of the convective model written as generalised, spacetime D'Alembertian (see, e.g., [8, 9]). More specifically, the local curvature of the spacetime is analysed by evaluating the value of the Ricci's scalar for simple background potential flows for which the velocity field is known analytically. The objective of the analysis is an interpretation of the effect of the $\mathcal{O}(M_\infty)$ approximation onto the convective structure of the equation. Section 2 introduces the nomenclature that will be used, whereas Section 3 describes the structure of the spacetime metrics associated to specific aerodynamic models. Results are presented in Section 4, followed by the concluding remarks in Section 5.

2. Aeroacoustic spacetime

The basic structure of the four-dimensional aeroacoustic spacetime where the analysis is carried out is presented here, as well as the properties of the operators adopted and their relationship with the standard tools used in the aeroacoustic context. In the following, the standard notation adopted in special and general relativity is used. Specifically, Greek superscripts varying from 0 to 3 are used to indicate variables and operators defined in the four-dimensional spacetime, whereas Latin superscripts varying from 1 to 3 are used for the standard three-dimensional space. Einstein summation convention on repeated indices is used throughout the paper, unless otherwise specified. A spacetime *event* (i.e., the “position of a point” in the spacetime) is identified by the four-vector $\xi = (\xi^0, \xi^1, \xi^2, \xi^3) \equiv (c_{\text{ref}}t, x^i) \in \mathbb{R}^4$. It is worth repeating that c_{ref} must be considered as a dimensional, invariant scaling constant to ensure consistency with the fundamental assumptions of special relativity, and that no hypotheses on the nature of the medium or on its status are implied at this point. In the following, c_{ref} will be chosen as the speed of sound in the undisturbed medium, c_∞ . Assuming the distances measured in second-sound it follows $c_{\text{ref}} = 1$. Indicating with $\partial_\mu = \partial/\partial\xi^\mu$ the covariant derivative with respect to ξ^μ , the four-gradient operator is the four-vector operator defined as $\partial = \partial_\nu g^\nu$, being g^ν an element of the contravariant basis. Let's initially assume that our spacetime is a “flat” four-dimensional space, i.e., a *Minkowski space*, that the ξ^α are a set of orthonormal, Cartesian-like coordinates. The separation of two events, P and Q , is denoted by the four-vector $\mathbf{u} = \xi_P - \xi_Q$ (see, e.g., Carroll [9] for a rigorous and complete introduction to spacetime differential geometry). The spacetime interval s separating the two events is given by

$$s^2 = \eta_{\mu\nu} u^\mu u^\nu, \quad \text{with } \eta_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & \vdots & 0 \\ \cdots & \cdot & \cdots \\ 0 & \vdots & \delta_{ij} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

where $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ is the *Minkowski* metric tensor, having signature (3, 1). One of the consequences of the structure of the Minkowski metric is that, in the spacetime context, covariant and contravariant basis vectors differ also for orthonormal coordinates on a flat manifold, i.e., $g^\nu = \eta^{\nu\mu} g_\mu$, with $\eta^{\nu\mu} \eta_{\mu\gamma} = \delta_\gamma^\nu$. Spacetime coordinate transformation leaving s unchanged are called *Lorentzian* transformations. Using matrix notation for notational simplicity, the condition that the transformation $\bar{\mathbf{u}} = \Lambda \mathbf{u}$ keeps s invariant gives

$$s^2 = \mathbf{u}^T \boldsymbol{\eta} \mathbf{u} = \bar{\mathbf{u}}^T \boldsymbol{\eta} \bar{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{u}^T \Lambda^T \boldsymbol{\eta} \Lambda \mathbf{u} \quad (2)$$

which in tensor notation is $\eta_{\mu\nu} = \Lambda_{\bar{\mu}}^{\bar{\nu}} \Lambda_{\nu}^{\bar{\mu}} \eta_{\bar{\mu}\bar{\nu}}$, and means that the metric tensor is represented by the same matrix in the two coordinate systems.

Within the spacetime context, the standard wave equation governing the propagation of the small fluctuations of the quantity φ within a quiescent medium can be expressed in the form

$$\partial_\mu (\eta^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu \varphi) = \partial_\mu \partial^\nu \varphi = 0 \quad (3)$$

where the contravariant components of the four–gradient operator are related to the time and space derivatives by $(-\partial_0, \partial_1, \partial_2, \partial_3) = (-\partial_t, \partial_i)$. Equation 3 is a particular case of the generalized D’Alembertian on a Lorentzian (or *pseudo–Riemannian*) manifold

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} \partial_\mu (\sqrt{-g} g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu \varphi) = 0 \quad (4)$$

where the inverse metric $g^{\mu\nu}$ has signature $(3, 1)$ and determinant $g < 0$. In presence of a background aerodynamic flow, the convective wave equation can be recast in the form of Eq. 4 with the a metric tensor that depends on the specific assumptions made on the background flow. In the following, the background flow will be assumed to be potential and stationary. The relationship between the local spacetime properties and the asymptotic Mach number M_∞ of the background flow will be the objective of the paper.

The local spacetime curvature can be expressed by the Riemann tensor

$$R_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = \partial_\gamma \Gamma_{\delta\beta}^\alpha - \partial_\delta \Gamma_{\gamma\beta}^\alpha + \Gamma_{\gamma\epsilon}^\alpha \Gamma_{\delta\beta}^\epsilon + \Gamma_{\delta\epsilon}^\alpha \Gamma_{\gamma\beta}^\epsilon \quad (5)$$

related to the metric by the Christoffel symbols of the second type

$$\Gamma_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha = \mathbf{g}_\alpha \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{g}^\beta}{\partial \xi^\gamma} = \frac{1}{2} g^{\alpha\lambda} (\partial_\beta g_{\gamma\lambda} + \partial_\gamma g_{\lambda\beta} - \partial_\lambda g_{\alpha\beta}) \quad (6)$$

Equations 5 and 6 show clearly how the curvature of the spacetime is not zero whenever the metric tensor is variable in space. In the present context, this is related to a non uniform aerodynamic velocity field. In the following, the information about the local spacetime curvature will be given in term of Ricci’s scalar $\mathcal{R} = \mathbf{g}^{\beta\delta} R_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\gamma$, which represents the change in volume of a small *Lorentzian* ball w.r.t. the corresponding *Euclidean* one.

3. Spacetime structure for different aerodynamic models

In the present Section, the influence of the specific aerodynamic model on the local structure of the spacetime is analysed for a simple benchmark case. The acoustic disturbance propagates in a moving medium with asymptotic Mach $M_\infty = v_\infty/c_\infty$ in presence of an impermeable obstacle. The latter induces an aerodynamic perturbation \mathbf{v}' , thus making the background flow speed non uniform, $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{v}_\infty + \mathbf{v}'(\mathbf{x})$. The governing equation will be written in classic notation and then reformulated into spacetime form. Indicating with $\varphi(\mathbf{x})$ the acoustic perturbation potential, the equation governing the propagation of an acoustic disturbance for an arbitrary (subsonic) Mach number M_∞ is

$$-\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left[\frac{\varrho_0}{c_0^2} \left(\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \varphi \right) \right] + \nabla \cdot \left[\varrho_0 \nabla \varphi - \frac{\varrho_0}{c_0^2} \left(\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \varphi \right) \right] = S \quad (7)$$

where ϱ_0 and c_0 are the local density and speed of sound of the background aerodynamic flow. For a potential flow, in absence of entropy sources, their ratio is

$$\frac{\varrho_0}{c_0^2} = \left[1 - \frac{\gamma - 1}{c_\infty^2} \frac{v^2}{2} \right]^{\frac{2-\gamma}{\gamma-1}} \quad (8)$$

where γ is the ratio of specific heats. The spacetime form of Eq. 7 is

$$-\partial_\alpha \left(\frac{\varrho_0}{c_0^2} \nu^\alpha \nu^\beta \partial_\beta \varphi \right) + \partial_k \varrho_0 \partial_k \varphi = S \quad (9)$$

with $\boldsymbol{\nu} = \{1, v^1, v^2, v^3\}^T$. It can be easily demonstrated that Eq. 9 is equivalent to 4 with

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\rho_0}{c_0} \begin{pmatrix} -(c_0^2 - v^2) & \vdots & -v^j \\ \cdots & \cdot & \cdots \\ -v^i & \vdots & \delta^{ij} \end{pmatrix}, \quad g^{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\rho_0 c_0} \begin{pmatrix} -1 & \vdots & -v^j \\ \cdots & \cdot & \cdots \\ -v^i & \vdots & c_0^2 \delta^{ij} - v^i v^j \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Equation 7 can be linearised for low Mach number background flows ($M_\infty^2 \ll 1$) to yield the linear convected wave equation

$$-\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla\right) \left(\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \varphi\right) + \nabla^2 \varphi = S \quad (11)$$

which can be written in form 4 with

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -(1 - v^2) & \vdots & -v^j \\ \cdots & \cdot & \cdots \\ -v^i & \vdots & \delta^{ij} \end{pmatrix}, \quad g^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & \vdots & -v^j \\ \cdots & \cdot & \cdots \\ -v^i & \vdots & \delta^{ij} - v^i v^j \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

Finally, exploiting the fact that the $\mathcal{O}(M_\infty)$ terms in Eq. 11 dominate, the $\mathcal{O}(M_\infty^2)$ can be neglected to obtain

$$-\frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial t^2} - 2 \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial t} + \nabla^2 \varphi = 0 \quad (13)$$

When the aerodynamic flow is potential, $\mathbf{v} = \nabla \Phi$, the spacetime metric tensor associated to Eq. 13 can be obtained by applying the Taylor transformation $\bar{\xi} = T(\xi)$ (Taylor [10]) to the metric of the static wave equation $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$. The spacetime form of the inverse Taylor transformation (for $c_{\text{ref}} = 1$) is

$$\bar{\xi}^0 = \xi^0 - \Phi(\xi^1, \xi^2, \xi^3) \quad (14)$$

$$\bar{\xi}^j = \xi^j \quad (15)$$

The effect of the transformation and its inverse is depicted in Fig. 1 for the acoustic field generated by a

Figure 1: Effect of the Taylor's coordinate transformation and its inverse.

point source in a uniform stream. Defining $\bar{\Lambda}_\mu^{\bar{\mu}} = \partial_\mu \bar{\xi}^{\bar{\mu}}$ the transformed contravariant metrics is obtained

as $\bar{g}^{\mu\nu} = \Lambda_{\mu}^{\bar{\mu}} \Lambda_{\nu}^{\bar{\nu}} g^{\mu\nu}$, to obtain

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & \vdots & -v^j \\ \cdots & \cdot & \cdots \\ -v^i & \vdots & \delta^{ij} - v^i v^j \end{pmatrix}, \quad g^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -(1 - v^2) & \vdots & -v^j \\ \cdots & \cdot & \cdots \\ -v^i & \vdots & \delta^{ij} \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

which to the order of M_{∞} becomes

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & \vdots & -v^j \\ \cdots & \cdot & \cdots \\ -v^i & \vdots & \delta^{ij} \end{pmatrix}, \quad g^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & \vdots & -v^j \\ \cdots & \cdot & \cdots \\ -v^i & \vdots & \delta^{ij} \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

The local structure of the spacetime for the above model is compared analysed and commented in the following section.

4. Numerical simulations

Let's assume that the impermeable obstacle is a circular cylinder and U_{∞} represents the asymptotic uniform stream velocity. The potential velocity field can be calculated analytically as

$$v^1 = U_{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2} \right), \quad v^2 = \frac{-2 U_{\infty} \xi_1 \xi_2}{(\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2)^2} \quad (18)$$

The velocity 18 is here used to evaluate the Ricci's scalar \mathcal{R} for all the models described in Section 3. Specifically, Figure 2 shows the value of the Ricci's scalar for metrics 10, whereas the plot in Figure 3 derives from Eq. 12 and that in Fig. 4 is related to the $\mathcal{O}(M_{\infty})$ metrics in Eq. 17.

Figure 2: Scalar curvature around the obstacle from metrics 10.

The difference is evident in terms of absolute value, overall shape and (what is more surprising) also in sign. The latter effect is unexpected since the sign of the scalar curvature is directly related to the ratio between the volume of the elementary Lorentzian ball and the corresponding Euclidean one. In general relativity, this sign is related to the local contraction ($\mathcal{R} > 0$) or expansion ($\mathcal{R} < 0$) of the spacetime. It is reasonable thinking that in the aeroacoustic context this sign indicates how the background aerodynamics acts on the acoustic perturbation, thus being related to the convection phenomenon. The preliminary result shown could induce the suspect that the linearised models may completely modify the modeling

Figure 3: Scalar curvature around the obstacle from metrics 12.

Figure 4: Scalar curvature around the obstacle from metrics 17.

of convection. This hypothesis is easily contradicted by the simple observation that all the linearised models analysed yield a good reproduction of the aerodynamic transport, provided that the assumption of low Mach is satisfied.

The only possible conclusion at the present stage of the research is that additional investigation is required to confirm, verify and clarify these preliminary results. In case that the observed behavior is confirmed by a more careful analysis also for other background flows, the more complete (and much more complicated) analysis of the Ricci tensor may be the only possible strategy.

5. Concluding remarks

The local structure of the aeroacoustic spacetime induced by different potential flow models has been analysed and numerically assessed for a simple benchmark problem. The local curvature induced by the metric of the full nonlinear equation for the propagation of an acoustic disturbance within a compressible potential flow has been calculated and compared with the one associated to its low Mach approximations. The analysis revealed that the low-Mach approximations modify substantially the local structure of the spacetime, also inducing a change of sign of the Ricci's scalar. This effect inverts the ratio between the measure of the spacetime Lorentzian elementary ball and the corresponding Euclidean one, thus inducing

the conclusion that the linearisation could modify substantially the convection effects associated to the models. Nevertheless, simple numerical experiments can easily show that the linearised, convected wave equation(s) accurately reproduce the aeroacoustic convection when the $M_\infty \ll 1$ condition is satisfied. Additional work is needed to clarify this point, possibly through the spectral analysis of the Ricci tensor.

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